

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF OUTDOOR GAMES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN'S MOTOR ACTIVITY

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Annotation

The presented article provides extensive information on the effectiveness of the use of open games in the development of children's activity, increasing their physical activity. Various changes that occur in their bodies during the game are also mentioned.

Keywords: physical loads, emotions, physical exertion, courage, determination, dexterity, intelligence, imagination.

Annotatsiya

Taqdim etilgan maqolada bolalar faolligini rivojlantirishda, ularning jismoniy faolligini oshirishda harakatli o'yinlardan foydalanish samaradorligi to'g'isida ma'lumotlar berilgan. Shuningdek, o'yin davomida ularning organizmida sodir bo'ladigan turli xil o'garishlar ham haqida ko'plab izohlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: jismoniy yuklamalar, hissiyotlar, jismoniy zo'riqish, jasorat, qat'iyatlilik, epcchillik, aql, tasavvur.

Аннотация

В представленной статье представлена обширная информация об эффективности использования открытых игр в развитии активности детей, повышении их физической активности. Также упоминаются различные изменения, которые происходят в их организме во время игры.

Ключевые слова: физические нагрузки, эмоции, физическое напряжение, смелость, решительность, ловкость, сноровистость, интеллект, воображение, фантазерка.

Outdoor play is one of the important means of comprehensive education of children. Its characteristic feature is the complexity of the impact on the body and on all sides of the child's personality: physical, mental, moral, aesthetic and labor education are simultaneously carried out in the game.

Active motor activity of a playful nature and the positive emotions it causes enhance all physiological processes in the body, improve the functioning of all organs and systems. Unexpected situations that arise in the game teach children to use the acquired motor skills expediently.

Outdoor games create the most favorable conditions for the development of physical qualities.

During the game, the children act in accordance with the rules that are mandatory for all participants. The rules regulate the behavior of the players and contribute to the development of mutual assistance, teamwork, honesty, discipline. At the same time, the need

to follow the rules, as well as overcome obstacles that are inevitable in the game, contributes to the education of strong-willed qualities - endurance, courage, determination, the ability to cope with negative emotions.

In outdoor games, the child has to decide for himself how to act in order to achieve the goal. The rapid and sometimes unexpected change of conditions forces more and more new ways to solve emerging problems. All this contributes to the development of independence, activity, initiative, creativity, and ingenuity. Games help the child to expand and deepen his ideas about the surrounding reality.

Outdoor games are also of great importance for moral education. Children are taught to act in a team, to obey common requirements. Children perceive the rules of the game as the law, and their conscious fulfillment forms the will, develops self-control, the ability to control their actions, their behavior. Honesty, discipline, and fairness are formed in the game. Outdoor play teaches sincerity and camaraderie. Obeying the rules of the game, children practically practice moral actions, teach them to be friends, empathize, and help each other. Skillful, thoughtful guidance of the game by the teacher contributes to the education of an active creative personality.

The specificity of the outdoor game consists in the lightning-fast, instantaneous response of the child to the signal "Catch!", "Run!", "Stop!" etc. Outdoor play is an indispensable means for a child to replenish knowledge and ideas about the world around him, develop thinking, wit, dexterity, valuable moral and volitional qualities. The child realizes freedom of action in outdoor games, which are the leading method of forming physical culture and sports. In pedagogical science, outdoor games are considered as the most important means of comprehensive development of a child. The deep meaning of outdoor games lies in their full-fledged role in the physical and spiritual life that exists in the history and culture of each nation.

Outdoor games also have a great influence on the neuropsychic development of the child, the formation of important personality qualities. They evoke positive emotions, develop inhibitory processes: during the game, children have to react with movement to some signals and refrain from moving with others. These games develop willpower, intelligence, courage, quick reactions, etc.

An active game with rules is a conscious, active activity of a child, characterized by accurate and timely completion of tasks related to the rules that are mandatory for all players. Outdoor play is an exercise through which a child prepares for life. The fascinating content and emotional intensity of the game encourage the child to make certain mental and physical efforts.

Outdoor play can be called the most important educational institution that promotes both the development of physical and mental abilities, as well as the development of moral norms, rules of conduct, and ethical values of society. Outdoor games are one of the conditions for the development of a child's culture. In them, he comprehends and learns about the world around him, his intellect, imagination, imagination develop in them, and social qualities are formed. Outdoor games are always a creative activity in which the child's natural need for movement is manifested, the need to find a solution to a motor task. By playing, the child not only learns about the world around him, but also transforms it.

Outdoor games are divided into elementary and complex ones. Elementary, in turn, are divided into plot and plotless, fun games, attractions.

In working with preschool children, so-called fun games and attractions are also used. Although they are not particularly important for physical development, they are, however, often held at leisure evenings, on physical culture holidays. Motor tasks in these games are performed in unusual conditions and often include an element of competition (running, holding a spoon with a ball in it, and not dropping anything; running in a bag; performing a blindfolded movement: hitting the ball with your foot, "watering the horse", etc.). Fun games at leisure evenings and holidays are a fun sight, entertainment for children, which gives them joy, but at the same time require motor skills, dexterity, and dexterity from participants.

Challenging games include sports games such as small towns, badminton, table tennis, basketball, volleyball, football, hockey. At preschool age, elements of these games are used and children play according to simplified rules.

Outdoor games also differ in their motor content: games with running, jumping, throwing, etc.

According to the degree of physical activity that each player receives, there are games of high, medium and low mobility.

Games of great mobility include those in which the whole group of children participates at the same time and they are built mainly on movements such as running and jumping.

Games of medium mobility are those in which the whole group actively participates, but the nature of the movements of the players is relatively calm (walking, passing objects) or the movement is performed by subgroups.

In games of low mobility, movements are performed at a slow pace, besides their intensity is insignificant.

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